

MODEL OF OPTIMIZATION OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-DEVELOPMENT OF A TEACHER IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Feruzza Sakhibova Askerovna

NamSU researcher

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Annotations: The article analyzes in detail the problems of motivation for professional search in modern psychology and pedagogy, offers and recommendations for solving this problem.

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Therefore, whether it is about understanding the nature of motivation, its role in the regulation of behavior, or about understanding the relationship between motivation and motivation to act, there is no consensus. In many works, these two concepts are used as synonyms. In this regard, motivation can be viewed as a dynamic process of formation of motivation.

The hierarchical structure of the motivational field determines the orientation of a person's personality, which has different characteristics, depending on what motivations have become dominant in its content and structure [1]. Motivation-motivation is an area of motivation, which is understood as a source of activity and, at the same time, as a system for stimulating any activity.

Motivation is studied in different ways, which is why the authors explain it differently. Researchers define it as a specific motivation, and as a single system of motivation, and as a special area that includes needs, motivations, goals and interests in their complex interweaving and interaction.

The explanation of motivation connects this concept with a need (drive), or experience with this need and its satisfaction, or with an object that is needed.

Therefore, in the context of the theory of activity of A.N. Leontiev's term "motive" is used not to denote the required experience, but to denote the goal that must be specified in the given conditions, and the goal to which the activity is directed as motivation [2].

It should be noted that, according to A.N. Leontiev, understanding motivation as "objectified needs" allows us to define it as internal motivation, which is part of the structure of the activity itself. The most complete is one of the main studies on this issue - the definition of motivation proposed by L.I. Bozovic. According to L.I. Bozhovich, motivation is what carries out activity, objects, ideas, thoughts, feelings and experiences of the outside world can be used as motivation [3]. Such a definition of motivation eliminates many contradictions in its interpretation, which combines bright, quivering and significant aspects. At the

same time, we emphasize that the concept of "motive" is already the concept of "motivation", which, as a complex mechanism for the correlation of external and internal factors of human behavior, determines the appearance, direction and method of implementing specific forms of activity.

The most extensive is the concept of the field of motivation, which includes a person in the areas of emotions and will, the experience of meeting needs.

Processing into a behavioral state that requires goals and plans is basically similar to the processing of weak sensory inputs into a meaningful perception of specific situations and objects (attention, a perceived object is needed in the required dynamic scheme, so this process can be described in four statements:

1. Demand not only influences human behavior by eliciting "trial and error" motor responses, but also by activating and directing the cognitive function of the subject, so that an object suitable to meet the demand can become a goal to be achieved. Therefore, the goal is to concretize or "concentrate" the demand.

2. Taking full advantage of its rich store of information and flexibility of operations, the subject's cognitive function develops a "means to an end" behavioral structure, that is, a behavioral blueprint or plan by which the goal can be achieved. Therefore, planning is a specific form of behavior that must be accepted at the achieved level of knowledge.

3. Before the goal is achieved, the subject perceives the difference (discrepancy) between the current situation and the desired goal. This difference in itself affects behavior not as motivation, but as information that needs have not yet been satisfied. Therefore, the subject retains motivation and must continue his purposeful activity. Inconsistency, like expected results, cannot replace motivation.

4. The transition from cognitive-dynamic goal-setting and planning to external behavioral actions should be considered in the context of a single function of individuals who have the motor and psychological potential to perform actions. A single innate motivation is the basis of two functional modes [4].

In addition to transforming needs into goals and action plans, cognitive processing of motivation leads to the personalization of motivation. To transform into goals and projects, you need to become a "person". The ultimate goal is the goal of the subject, and the act of achieving the result is also the action of the subject. This personalization process will affect the dynamic and normative characteristics of the target.

Motivation is characterized by the target orientation of demand. According to J. Nutten, the main direction of demand is innate, but it develops and materializes in countless specific motivations and goals. At the same time, the intensity of

motivation depends on the nature of the demand and the attitude of the individual to the demand. Fulfilling a requirement is not just about following the action, but also about the need to direct the action. Consequently, the personality itself forms a repertoire of actual needs, which triggers the mechanism of motivational behavior.

Cognitive processing of the transformation of needs into behavioral forms is the critical moment when motivation appears. Through the activation of cognitive functions, individuals in a state of need strive to implement personally constructed goals and plans in behavior and activity. Thus, the needs become personal constructs, and the goals of self-construction become the criteria for evaluating actions. Even external factors influence a person's behavior so strongly that they are positively or negatively evaluated in terms of personal standards. Personalization of motivation and self-regulation of behavior are considered the result of individuals' cognitive processing of their own behavior and behavioral dynamics [5].

The main task of developing a relational model of behavior and its dynamics is to show the unity of cognition, motivation and motor function in a single behavioral process. Therefore, in the behavioral world and the construction of behavioral actions, cognitive and motivational processes play an important role, while the dynamics of behavior are processed cognitively and specific actions are taken in external relations with the significant world.

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